

Study of Work Performance of Senior Secondary School Teachers of Khargone District

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ABSTRACT

The objective of research was to study the Work Performance of Senior Secondary School teachers of Khargone District. The research was survey type in nature. Twelve Senior Secondary Schools of Khargone District were selected randomly in the study. Total 158 Teachers from these schools were used in the sample. Five Point teacher Work Performance Scale was developed by the Researcher for data collection. The data were analyzed by the Mean. The Work Performance of teachers was found very satisfactory for different aspects of Work Performance. The overall Work Performance was found 4.13. It indicated that Work Performance of teachers was found very satisfactory.

Key Words : Work Performance, Senior Secondary School, Teacher & Khargone

Introduction

Teachers' work performance in school has important role in achieving the goal of school. According to Wahab & Umiarso (2011), teachers' work performance is an ability shown by teachers in implementing their duties or works. "Teacher performance is the ability to apply its competence in the performance of its duties which include learning to plan, implement learning and assess learning outcomes". (Kempa & Herenz, 2016). Teacher work performance refers to the quality and quantity of work a teacher achieves while fulfilling their duties and responsibilities, encompassing their ability to plan, implement, and evaluate learning, as well as their skills in classroom management, communication, and professional development. Teacher's performance could be improved through

attitude modification, work motivation, and favorable organizational culture in schools. Some teachers were afraid that they did not have skills necessary for teaching children but for some, creating a healthy learning environment is of paramount concern and challenges faced during. To enhance the performance of teachers in the teaching-learning process, the school has to invest and allocate an adequate amount for the professional development program of all teachers. They should not be confined only in the four walls of the classroom, but they have to be allowed to keep abreast of all the updates in teaching. They are duty bound to work with other people in the community aside from doing daily routines in education. Thus, training and workshops whether in local, national or international that promote the better performance of teachers in teaching and in fostering activities that attract the people in the community to participate for the betterment of the school are necessary.

.Objective

The objective of research was to study the Work Performance of Senior Secondary School teachers of Khargone District.

Methodology

The research was survey type in nature. Twelve Senior Secondary Schools of Khargone District were selected randomly in the study. Total 158 Teachers from these schools were used in the sample. Teacher Work Performance Scale was developed by the Researcher. The five point Outstanding, Very Satisfactory, Satisfactory, Fair and Poor used in Scale for data collection. The various aspect of Work Performance was included in the Scale. The names of aspect of Work Performance were – Teaching learning process, Pupils' outcomes, Community involvement & Professional growth and development. The data were analysed with the help of Mean.

Result and Interpretation

The objective of research was to study the Work Performance of Senior Secondary School teachers of Khargone District. The mean score for various aspects of Work Performance of teachers are given below in table 1.

Table 1 : Mean Score of Work Performance of teachers on WP-Scale

Aspect of Work Performance (WP)	Mean
Teaching learning process	4.03
Pupils' outcomes	4.23
Community involvement	4.17
Professional growth and development	4.09
Over all Work Performance	4.13

It is clear from table 1 that the Work Performance of teachers was found satisfactory for different aspects of Work Performance. The range of different aspects of Work Performance is 4.03 to 4.23. The lowest mean score is 4.03 for Teaching Learning Process aspect while highest mean score is 4.23 for Pupils' Outcome aspect of Work Performance. The mean score for Community involvement & Professional growth and development were found 4.17 & 4.09 respectively. The overall Work Performance was found 4.13. It indicated that Work Performance of teachers is very satisfactory.

Delimitations

- (1) Only Private Schools' teachers were taken in this study.
- (2) Khargone District Schools teachers were taken in this study.
- (3) Hindi & English Medium Schools' teachers were taken in this study.

- (4) M.P. Board Schools' teachers were taken in this study.

References

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